

CHANGE IN ATTITUDE: MANAGING STRESS THROUGH SOAR MODEL

Reena Nigam¹, Sunil K. Mishra²

¹HoD, Amity Skills Institute, Amity University Haryana. rnigam@ggn.amity.edu

²Associate Professor (English), Amity School of Liberal Arts, Amity University, Haryana. skmishra@ggn.amity.edu

Received: 12.04.2020

Revised: 19.05.2020

Accepted: 10.06.2020

Abstract

Stress is the most widely used term in the present scenario. Everyone is stressed irrespective of their location, job, age or gender. One may wonder if we are allowing ourselves to become a victim of stress because it may be related to a fad which describes one's social status and worth. It may have become a part of societal perception of job demands and is akin to our happiness quotient. We live in an intense age where, one is expected to 'be all' and 'know all'. In such an age, the chances are that we are trying to find an escape route by declaring ourselves 'stressed' as if we are suffering from a terminal disease which has no cure. Stress is palpable in even children and people who have willingly decided to go without work, but are in the race anyway. In such a scenario one may not dismiss the possibilities that we are all becoming victims of a social bug to which people relate their sense of worthiness and the cure may lie within each individual. In a recent survey done by the author, it was discovered that in important sectors like Aviation, Construction, Apparel and Automotive, about 50% respondents, who belonged to senior management, fell into the category of low optimism levels. This reflected in their behavior, interpersonal skills and ability to communicate too. If an individual is showing so many lows in one's attitude, it is natural that the person will be prone to stresses too. In this fast developing, technology driven, dynamic world, an individual finds himself in a race which one can't always win. The competition is not only with the fellow workers but also with the machines and disruptive technology. Every day one feels rendered redundant in one or many ways at work place. Either there is a smarter person posing competition or a smarter device. In such a scenario one may find stress as a resort to halt. The flight and fight syndrome looks for a habitat in the more negative road of stress and stressors. The objective of this paper is to discuss how to manage stress through Spiritualism, Optimism, Acceptance and Rationalism (SOAR) model.

Keywords: Spiritualism, Optimism, Acceptance, Rationalism, Stress-management.

© 2020 by Advance Scientific Research. This is an open-access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)
DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.11.147>

INTRODUCTION

A change in attitude may be the answer to deal with it. We all know that the job demands, work pressures and societal pressures will remain. What we need to find is the way to detach ourselves from them-not in the old 'Himalaya way' of renunciation but by bringing a change in the self. We need to teach ourselves the art of winning without being in the race. Altering our attitude through self help could be the key.

It is no exaggeration that stress is one unshakable appendage of human life and there is no human being who is not affected by it, irrespective of age, gender and profession. It would not be out of context to quote Selye who thought that stress is a part of living and the name of stress free life is death. (selye, 1974) If we go on to analyze the causes of these stresses the long list would consist of a frivolous argument with the spouse, traffic snarls, and, could also include many big and small events in life. A rebuke from the boss, even if not career threatening, can affect an individual drastically. Similarly a minor technical glitch in the office can cause a big heart burn on the day of an important meeting. The small incidents of annoyance can lead to big distress. Stress, therefore, has a really wide range. So much so that when Selve was asked to define stress in his later years he quipped, everyone knows what stress is, but nobody really knows.

One can't really change the stress causing events in personal and professional life. Most of these events catch us unaware and leave us with no option but to face them and bear them. But the frightful fact is that these minor incidents cost us our mental and physical health. In an article, Jennifer Breheny Wallace stated that when people talk about stresses they are mostly talking about the big events and the minor events are forgotten. But minor events that happen in everyday life are the real game changers. (Wallace, 2018) We get so burdened with the weight of negative events that the happy events are forgotten and stress takes the forefront. During the relaxed hours we keep thinking of

the stresses that we would be facing in future. In other words, our life is completely dominated by stresses. The word stress has become an oft repeated term in our vocabulary. Children in primary schools, and even younger, are suffering from anxiety and stress. Work related stress may have taken our notice the most but, people who are unconnected with work like housewives and young students are using the words as often as the working professionals, if not more.

The unfortunate fact is that stress related support system works only for big stress causing events like loss of a loved one, pink slip from job, failure in exams etc. These events are noticed and communication is encouraged around them which may help in healing. The chain of annoyances that we go through in daily life gets ignored. Frequent occurrences like traffic snarls, power failures, and technical troubles, disagreement with the companion or colleagues are like slow poison that slowly and steadily affect us and create health issues like hypertension, diabetes, respiratory problems and heart ailments. People neither talk about them nor like to hear about them. Therefore, these problems go unresolved and trapped in our built in system.

Senior managers and leaders are probably the biggest victims of stress. They take the maximum pressure of work and are also expected to be the firefighters. People look up to them for problem resolution and are expected to be in the know of all and sundry. Therefore they fall prey to not only their own stressors but also what people make them part of. It is a huge role to play and justify. Yet, people from lower ranks look at them as, exploiters and view them with suspicion.

Leaders are always in a firefighting zone, which means their decisions affect others which can cause acute stress due to personal accountability. Similarly, research has proved that people who have to perform under time pressures or those who perform multiple tasks experience much stress. (Finucane, Alhakami, Slovik, & Johnson, 2000)

It can also be supported by Beck's theory, according to which, personalization of negative events can lead to stress, which includes negative views of the self like "I am worthless" and "There is no hope for me" or "Nobody likes me" (Beck, Beck, Rush, Shaw, & Emery, 1979)

Yet, we all know that stress at job can cost heavily. It can result in lower productivity, reduced motivation and job skills and also in increased errors and accident.

Lazarus and Folkman also have similar views. As per them, the internal cognitive processes have psychological perspectives. People judge external events in relation to their own goals, achievement and resources and perceive them as negative. Such perspectives have definite stress elements. (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). In such scenario, it is but natural that leaders suffer from stress. In this study we are going to quote a recent study by the author, which brought out the fact that after a survey done to measure the optimism index, as an attitude, in leaders, it was found out that leaders suffer from issues related to anxiety, confidence and communication. They appeared to be lacking in dimensions of Positive emotions, engagement, relationship network, meaningfulness and achievement. The result of which may be stress.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the paper are the following:

- Understanding causes of stress at workplace
- Creating a model to deal with modern day stress

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Causes for Stress

We live in a complex age and need to deal with many contradictions- external and internal. The causes may be studied as under:

a. Modern Society is Complex and Full of Contradiction

Yuji Kuroda, in his study, talked about attitudes and maladaptive beliefs which he termed as 'If then' and must statements. Some of the examples were, "If I am not loved by everyone then I am not worthy", "I must be the best", and if I am not good in a subject I am bound to fail'. These are some of the examples that we burden ourselves with. Such statements guide cognitive operations like perception, encoding, attention in negatively biased ways. This brings our focus towards excessive negative possibilities. In other words this can be termed as selective abstraction and arbitrary inference. A person tends to encode information in a negative biased way through self reference. (Yuji, 2016 beliefs). The individuals with dysfunctional attitudes in interpersonal and achievement domain have higher chances of stress. (Simons, Angell, Monoroe, & Thase, 1993)

b. Technological Disruptions

Technology is the necessary evil which has made the work easier but also brought with itself evils like fear of redundancy and fear of losing one's job. It is easier to compete with a human compared to a machine. Yet, at times you can't do without it. If one of them breaks down there is a huge amount of stress and tension involved because we immensely depend on them.

Social media and its various applications have added to the woes of a working man. The information galore, that it is afflicted with, causes tremendous amount of stress in humans. Multiple flow of communication is another calamity that humans have to face. Although technology and social media have made life easy and communication fast, irresponsible uses can prove disastrous. Now a leader has to deal with stream of negative emotions generated by the irresponsible use of social media. It generates a lot of grapevine too which can go out of control, at times. (Banerjee, Adhikari, & Nigam, 2016)

c. Challenges at Work

Burdens of quick decision making, personal goals, pressure to delegate, creating an atmosphere of harmony are some of the challenges faced by leaders. They need to live up to an image which may not be a smooth ride at times. Michael Useem in his research pointed out that under preparation, acute stress and ambiguous authority can result in errors in decision making amongst leaders. (Michael, Cook, & Sutton, 2005)

Competition at work clearly leads in office and workplace stress. Fair competition can stimulate motivation and prove positive stress. It may help a worker understand the aspects of job and excel in it. But, irrational and unjustified competition may lead to stress and adversely affect its subjects, lowering their productivity and potential. (Brate, 2004)

Demands at work can be challenging too. Sometimes there is an imbalance between the demands of work environment and the ability of an individual to meet them. (Issabella, 2009) Issabella also mentioned monotony at work as cause of stress. She calls it under stimulation. People working in assembly lines, data entry jobs and those who are under- utilized are generally the victims.

Another line of thought says that organizations are hugely responsible for their employees stress. (Henkoff, 2009). (Floyd & Wooldridge, 2012) compared the level of job satisfaction to level of stress. The less the satisfaction at work place, the more the stress.

In another study (Jones, 2011) stated that decision making determines the extent of satisfaction. In organizations where decision making is encouraged have less employees who are victims of stress. (Kozlowski, Chao, Smith, & Hedlund, 2013) created a direct link between prevention of decision making in employees and occupational stress.

(Muirhead, 2013) brought out the fact that restriction on freedom of individual's autonomy and identity are grave causes of stress at workplace. In the same line (Mayer, Smith, & Whittington, 2012) stated that role ambiguity and role conflicts are two main causes of stress. The uncertainties that the employees feel due to role ambiguities manifest in the psychological ailments they suffer. The lack of clarity also leads to deterioration of performance.

In a very interesting article in 'Time' (Baumnohl, 2013) described high demand at work and excessive quantity of work and time pressures as the culprit for stress, depression and anxiety at workplace.

Similar were the findings at the research conducted by us. The research conducted on 200 senior professionals proved that leaders suffer from high levels of stress.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A psychometric tool, 'Optimism index was used on 200 respondents in senior positions working in sectors like Aviation, Construction, Automotive and Apparel. The 60 questions contained in optimism index tested respondents on 5 dimensions called PEROMA. PEROMA is the acronym for Positive emotions, Engagements, Relationship Network, Meaningfulness and Achievements. It is well researched that the above dimensions have a direct implication on an individual's work efficacy, productivity and motivation. People, low on above dimensions, are also found to be low in their confidence, efficacy, motivation and productivity. These people are also prone to stresses and depression. On the other hand people with high levels of optimism are practical, accepting, rational and have belief in themselves.

Questionnaires were sent to the select population through Google forms. Almost 500 respondents were contacted out of which 200 responses were received. The number of responses received from each sectors were as followed:

Total valid sample size was N= 200

Other than the sectors and designation of a senior position no other criteria was specified during sample collection. In order to gather demographic details of the sample, a section on personal details viz, age, gender, Family type and designation was also included in the questionnaire.

Respondents from Aviation were mostly pilots at the levels of Captains and commanders. Some respondents from Aviation also belonged to the HR of major Indian aviation companies like Jet Airways, Indigo and Spicejet. No specific geographical zone was chosen as the respondents belonged to senior positions in their respective organizations and it was expected that they would generate cosmopolitan cultural responses. In Construction, majority of the respondents belonged to a giant multinational company and are posted in different states of India and some abroad. Respondents from Apparel mainly belonged to Delhi NCR and belonged to a milieu of garment export houses, entrepreneurs and retail. Respondents from Automotive industry also were majorly from Delhi NCR with a long and rich experience in the industry. All respondents, irrespective of their sectors belonged to a vast variety in their demographic range and are in the age groups of 25- 65.

a. Optimism Index

In our analysis it was seen that more than 50% leaders, in the given population, fell into the threshold and below category of optimism level. What it entails is the fact that these people are at a level where they are vulnerable to stresses, frustrations and depression. (Banerjee, P 2018)

b. Analysis

Optimism Index Scores Analysis

Table 1: Optimism Index score sheet

Range	Category	Normal Name
100 - 130	Red	7
131 - 170	Orange	6
171 - 200	Yellow	5
201 - 230	Green	4
231 - 250	Blue	3
251 - 275	Indigo	2
276 - 300	Violet	1

The above table describes the scoring of Optimism index wherein the lowest score is 100 and maximum is 300. Violet is the category for those who score in the range between 276-300 and denotes very high optimism level. Intense Indigo, in the range of 221-275, denotes next level of optimism which is followed by Brilliant Blue which falls in the range of 231-250. Gravitating Green which is in the range of 201-230 is the threshold level of optimism and is the beginning of the lower groups at optimism levels. People falling into Yellow, orange and Red belong to the low categories of optimism. At these levels intervention becomes necessary for an individual as it means severe break down of a person's optimism level. It also shows high levels of stress in them.

Chart 1: Classification based on global Scores of Optimism Index

Chart 2: Optimism levels in percentage

The above pie chart and the graph show that out of a sample size of 200 leaders from Aviation, Apparel, Construction and Automotive, only 4 people belong to the highest level of Optimism which is Violet. 34 people belong to Indigo which is next and 64 people belong to blue. The categories belong to the upper level which is above threshold level of optimism. A whopping 81 senior officials belong to threshold levels and 11 belong to yellow which shows poor level of optimism. What's more disconcerting is the fact that 3 seniors belonged to orange and Red which means the bottom of optimism and is threatening.

Findings

Following facts were extracted from the study:

1. People with high levels of optimism were confident
2. High levels also indicated their belief in themselves
3. Such people accept their circumstances and move on
4. They are able to see their difficult situation as temporary and continue to look forward to a brighter future
5. They are able to rationalize their circumstances and know that the problems are the result of specific circumstances
6. Such people are able to reason out and find a rationale in the face of crisis

Table 2: Scoring table for dimensions

Score	Energy Levels
<=30	Low
31 - 40	Threshold
41 - 50	Medium
51 - 60	High

The above table describes the scoring of PEROMA. People less than 30 are at a low level. Between 31-40 are at the threshold level and 41-50 are medium. Finally, people who are high at a particular dimension have a score which is between 51-60. The dimensions of PEROMA are Positive emotions, Engagement, Relationship network, Meaningfulness and Achievement.

SOAR MODEL AND STRESS MANAGEMENT

Based on the above findings the author created a model which consisted of the four major elements that help a person sustain during the time of the crisis. Stress can be a significant factor in performance and how a person may live his/her life. It has been a constant endeavour of psychologist to find a panacea to deal with stress. Coping can depend a lot on the cause of stress. In his study (Moos, 1992) divided stress coping strategies into emotion focused and problem focused. In our study we created a model consisting of Spiritualism, Optimism, Acceptance and Rationalization (SOAR). The four dimensions of SOAR can help people deal with the stress effectively. The best part is that through a little self help and consciousness the success can be attained. We will now discuss our model:

(i) Spiritualism

The lofty Spiritualism can be the answer to deal with stress. The idea of spirit uniting with the universe practiced through 'Yoga' can reduce the mental fatigue, experienced in the world, and transcend the mind to a more calming stage of blissfulness. Believing in some higher power transports the mind to a more exhilarating experience where worldly worries appear small. Meditation, Yoga and other such practices have a very soothing effect on humans. In a research conducted in the state of Kerala, it was proved that yoga and meditation are the most effective stress management practices among the executives in the private sector in Kerala. (Jayarajan, Stress management practices among executives in the private sector in Kerala, 2016)

Similarly, mindful meditation is also a unique way to confront the problem consciously and trying to find a solution.

(ii) Optimism

Optimism is an attitude that equips one to deal with crisis. People who suffer from lower levels of optimism are prone to stresses. The good news is that optimism can be developed if a conscious effort is made either with self help or with external support. In a book by Dr. Padmakali Banerjee, the author very categorically states that optimism can be developed. She suggested a model – Optimism attitude model (OAM) which can help people develop and enhance their levels of optimism. OAM is a cyclic model which takes one from the stage of self awareness to improving one's cognitive abilities towards higher levels of Optimism (Banerjee, The power of positivity: Optimism and the seventh sense, 2018).

(iii) Altruism/Acceptance

It is often the fear of losing power and position that causes stress. Altruism is associated with a feeling of selflessness. If one can practice putting others first before self the stress will drastically reduce. Although, it is easier said than done, because, human ego is the all powerful and all pervasive emotion. But it is also not impossible to achieve. Once it is understood that most of our stress related woes are the result of keeping ourselves on top, egos can be defeated.

Closely associated with altruism is the feeling of 'acceptance'. If we are made to understand that stresses are a way of life and the only way to attain victory over it is to accept them instead of getting overpowered by them, the stress may reduce. This theory is endorsed by (Mesko, 2013) who used eight CRI sub scales to assess coping strategy. First of which was –Logical analysis. It mentally prepares for the stressors and its consequences. Communication can also be a tool here. Talking to people and understanding what they are going through in their lives help people assimilate their own situation. Their might be a realization that it is not so bad and they are part of a universal system where everyone goes through the hardships.

(iv) Rationalism

(Mesko, 2013) also emphasized on rationalization. Powerful emotions lose their significance if rationalized. He suggested positive appraisal which involves accepting the problem and collecting the support system to solve it. It entails interpreting the problem in a positive way. This may entail a situation where a person is made to understand why he is going through a certain level of stress and what could be done to improve the situation. Sometimes it can be proved, again through communication and counseling, that the very problem that is giving stress is imaginary. A little practice of rationalizing a stress giving problem may put the victim into a pattern where he/she rationalizes every problem and avoid getting into stress.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded by emphasizing on the fact that stresses are unavoidable and will remain. It depends on an individual as to how much one allows stresses to burden them. How one can

control stress may have the answers within us. Acceptance, rationalization, communication and optimism are some of the obvious tools that can work like armor for us to shield ourselves with. It is easy to let ourselves be a victim. But how much we want to succeed in life will depend on what best we can do to face the stresses and deal with them.

REFERENCES

- Banerjee, P. (2018). *The Power of Positivity: Optimism and the Seventh Sense*. New Delhi: Sage.
- Banerjee, P., Adhikari, B., & Nigam, R. (2016). Dynamics of Workplace Communication: A New Age Model. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 1-16.
- Baumnohl, B. (2013). *When Downsizing Becomes Dumbsizing*. New York: Time.
- Beck, A. T., Rush, J., Shaw, B. F., & Emery, G. (1979). *Cognitive Therapy of Depression*. New York: Guildford Press.
- Bhattacharya, S. (2014, September 12). Hero Moto corp Gurgaon Plant Workers in Talks for Wage Hike. Gurgaon, Haryana, India. Retrieved August 23, 2016, from <http://www.firstpost.com>
- Bourne, L., & Bourne, E. (1966). Comments on Proessor CM Bilodean's paper. New York: New York Academic.
- Brate, A. (2004). *Diagnoza Multidimensională a Stresului Ocupational la manageri*. *Revista de psihologie Organizatională*, 3-4.
- Caroll, A. B. (2006, July 29). Trust is the Key When Rating Great Workplace. Retrieved from onlineathens.com: http://onlineathens.com/stories/073006/business_20060730047
- Cherunilam, F. (2011). *Business Environment*. Mumbai: Himalaya Publishing House, Pvt Ltd.
- Choudhry, C., & Jose, P. (2015, Feb 13). Workers Riot at Udyog Vihar in Gurgaon. Gurgaon, Haryana, India. Retrieved August 13, 2016, from <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com>
- Finucane, M. L., Alhakami, A., Slovik, P., & Johnson, S. M. (2000). The Affect of Heuristic in Judgements of Risks and Benefits. *Journal of Behavioural Decision Making*, 1-17.
- Floyd, S., & Wooldridge, B. (2012). Dinosaurs or Dynamos? Recognizing Middle Management's Strategic Role. *Academy of Management Executive*, 47-57.
- Henkoff, R. (2009). Cost cutting: How to do it Right. *Fortune*. Vol. 119, 40-49.
- Issabella, L. (2009). Downsizing: Survivors' Assessment *Business Horizons*. Vol. 32, 35-41.
- Jacob, M., Jacob, A., Feldman, G., & Cavior, N. (1973). Feedback II. The Credibility Gap: Delivery of Positive and Negative and Emotional and Behavioral Feedback in Groups. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 41,215-223.
- Jayarajan, T. (n.d.).
- Jayarajan, T. (2016). *Stress Management Practices Among Executives in Private Sector of Kerala*. Cochin: Cochin College.
- Jones, G. (2011). *The History of the British Bank of the Middle East*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kozlowski, S., Chao, G., Smith, E., & Hedlund, J. (2013). Organizational Downsizing: Strategies, Interventions and Research Implications. *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 263-332.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, Appraisal and Coping*. New York: Springer.
- Mayer, M., Smith, A., & Whittington, R. (2012). *Organizing for Success in the 21st Century, CEO's and HR Managers Perceptions*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.

22. Mesko, M. (2013). Relationship Between Stress Coping Strategies and Absenteeism among Middle Level Managers. *Management*, vol 18, 45-57.
23. Michael, U., Cook, J., & Sutton, L. (2005). Developing Leaders for Decision Making Under Stress: Wildlife firefighters in the South Canyon fire and its Aftermath. *Academy of management learning and education*, 461-485.
24. Moos, R. (1992). *Coping Responses Inventory Manual*. Windsor: In Milne, D.L. (Ed.) *Assessment: A Mental Health portfolio*.
25. Muirhead, S. (2013). *Crisis Banking in the East: The History of the Chartered Mercantile Bank of India, London and China*. Scholar Press, pp. 1853-93.
26. Mukherjee, S. (2012, December 21). Has Maruti Found a Solution for its Labour Woes? Gurgaon, Haryana, Country. Retrieved December 12, 2016, from <http://www.business-standard.com>
27. Reuben, D. (2014). *A Study on Impact of Training in IT Industry*. Madurai: Madurai Kamraj University.
28. Saleem, S. (2006). *Business Environment*. New Delhi: Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt. Ltd.
29. Selye, H. (1974). *Stress without Distress*. Philadelphia: J.B Lippincott.
30. Simons, A., Angell, K., Monroee, S., & Thase, M. (1993). Cognition and Life Stress in Depression: Cognitive Factors and the Definition, Rating, and Generation of Negative Life Events. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 584-591.
31. Sinha, S. (2015, September 19). Air India Pilots' Strike Threat Blows Over. New Delhi, National Capital Region, India. Retrieved November 24, 2016, from <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com>
32. Wallace, J. B. (2018, March 03). Even the Small Stress in Life can Hurt You but Attitude Can Make a difference. Washington, Washington, United states.
33. Walther, J. B. (2004). Language and Communication Technology. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 384-396.
34. Wikipedia. (2013, April 13). Wikipedia. Retrieved March 6th, 2018, from Wikipedia: <https://en.wikipedia.org>
35. Yuji, K. (2016 beliefs). Dysfunctional Attitudes are Maladaptive. *The Journal of Psychology*, 358-370.